

A Closer Look at Teachers' Demographic Challenges: Reflections from School Guidance Advocates

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Abstract. The purpose of the study was to determine the insights of school guidance advocates regarding the impact of demographic differences on professional challenges. On the quantitative part, a total of 66 guidance advocates in Caraga North District, Division of Davao Oriental were identified through Tabachnick and Fidell. Meanwhile, seven guidance advocates were used for the qualitative findings. The study utilized an explanatory sequential mixed method design. Frequency and percentage, mean, and thematic content analysis were used as statistical tools of the study. Results revealed on the demographic-based differences of guidance advocates in terms of age results revealed that the majority of school heads were aged 41–50 years old. Moreover, in terms of educational qualification results revealed that the majority of guidance advocates were MA graduates. Further, on the level of the challenges faced by teachers based on the school guidance advocates were oftentimes evident. On the qualitative data, three themes emerged after the thematic content analysis. On the insights of school guidance advocates regarding the impact of demographic differences on their professional challenges are: (1) developing healthy coping strategies, (2) encouraging collaboration, and (3) seeking help and support. Thus, this study suggests that guidance advocates should continue to provide ongoing support for teachers, especially in times of high stress or workload. They are encouraged to develop programs focused on resilience, coping strategies, and fostering collaboration among educators.

KEY WORDS

1. Guidance Advocates 2. Demographic Challenges 3. Teachers

4. Explanatory Sequential Design 5. Division of Davao Oriental, Philippines

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1. Introduction

The field of teaching is pivotal to the advancement of subsequent generations, necessitating a combination of knowledge, abilities, and adaptability to address the varied requirements of pupils. However, the efficiency of educators can be affected by various factors, such as educational background. Although teaching is universally challenging, the difficulties encountered by teachers may vary across different age

groups and levels of educational achievement. In such instances, the function of guidance advocates is essential. Guidance advocates, providing counsel, mentorship, and support, are crucial in confronting such challenges. These advocates actively assist teachers and can discern particular needs or areas for development that may not be easily identifiable.

In the international setting, Sumra (2023)

noted that in Tanzania, numerous teachers in government-run institutions encounter difficulties concerning remuneration, as the reduction in public social services has adversely affected their salaries. The loss of rent, incentive, transportation, and teaching allowances has resulted in inadequate salaries and diminished status. Educators perceive that their concerns are overlooked, resulting in dissatisfaction and a deterioration in educational quality, especially student learning outcomes. In this context, guidance advocates can assist educators in obtaining accessible resources or maneuvering through administrative processes to handle their issues regarding salary and allowances. By ensuring that educators feel supported and acknowledged, guidance advocates alleviate the detrimental impacts of the challenges teachers encounter on the quality of learning.

In Davao City, Lucernas (2024) identified that teachers encounter challenges such as dishonesty, disruptive behavior, and pupils' propensity for distraction, particularly due to their age. Students' academic performance is affected by truancy, tardiness, and persistent absences. To promote academic integrity, guidance advocates can lead workshops and help teachers discourage cheating. They can track attendance, work with families to reduce absenteeism, and create academic achievement initiatives.

The daily lives of public-school teachers are formed by a complex mixture of personal, professional, and classroom challenges. While plenty of research has been conducted on the general challenges that educators confront, there is a significant gap in studies that particularly address the issue from the perspective of school guidance advocates. Guidance advocates, who work closely with teachers, are uniquely positioned to understand and address these challenges. Given their direct interactions, they often have valuable insights into the issues affecting teachers. Therefore, the researcher aims to focus on this gap, emphasizing how

addressing these concerns can significantly enhance both teacher well-being and efficacy.

The main purpose of this study was to determine the demographic profile of teachers in terms of age and educational qualification. It also sought to assess the level of professional challenges encountered by teachers as perceived by school guidance advocates, focusing on four key areas: workload challenges, instructional challenges, social status and identity challenges, and challenges in relationships with colleagues. Furthermore, the study intended to examine whether there are significant differences in the professional challenges faced by teachers when grouped according to their demographic characteristics. Lastly, it aimed to gather and analyze the insights of school guidance advocates on how demographic differences influence the professional experiences and challenges of teachers within the district.

This study offers valuable insights and practical recommendations that benefit various stakeholders by enhancing policies, improving practices, and advancing overall progress in education. Students benefited from improved instructional practices and learning environments as teachers, supported by guidance advocates, were better equipped to meet their needs. Teachers gained a deeper understanding of the challenges they face, particularly across diverse demographics, and how guidance counselors can support their professional growth and well-being.

Figure 1 illustrated the conceptual framework delineating the study's variables. It showed that the input comprised two main variables which were: Demographic-based Differences and Challenges Faced by Teachers Based on Guidance Advocates. On the other hand, the output was the insights of school guidance advocates regarding the impact of teachers' demographic differences on their professional challenges in Caraga North District, Division of Davao Oriental.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design —This study used an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, collecting quantitative data through surveys followed by qualitative data via interviews to clarify and expand on the numerical results (Creswell Creswell, 2023). The quantitative phase focused on how demographic differences influence teachers’ challenges, while the qualitative phase explored guidance advocates’ perspectives for deeper insight. This approach integrated statistical trends with personal experiences to provide a comprehensive understanding of the problem.

2.2. Ethical Considerations —The study adhered strictly to ethical standards set by the RMC Research Ethics Committee, ensuring participants’ privacy, safety, and informed consent throughout the research process. With a focus on the challenges faced by teachers as observed by school guidance advocates, the study prioritized transparency, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Special attention was given to vulnerable participants, and potential conflicts

of interest were managed with neutrality. The researcher, qualified and guided by experts, used secure facilities and ethical protocols to protect data and participant well-being. By promoting justice, inclusivity, and open communication, the study contributed responsibly to educational research and practice.

2.3. Research Respondents —The study surveyed 66 guidance advocates from Caraga North District, Davao Oriental, selected using Tabachnick and Fidell’s (2007) formula to ensure reliable data on demographics and teachers’ professional challenges. Seven advocates were purposively chosen for interviews to gain detailed insights, based on their expertise and relevant training in counseling and teacher support, including recognized programs like Psychosocial Support Training, Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Training, and Psychological First Aid. Only advocates with such professional development were included to ensure informed perspectives, while those without were excluded to maintain study integrity.

2.4. *Research Instrument* —Quantitative data were collected using an adapted survey questionnaire validated by experts and pilot-tested for reliability. The survey included demographic questions adapted from Asi and Macarandang (2020) and measured teachers' challenges across workload, instructional issues, social status, and colleague relationships with 5-item scales. The qualitative phase used a researcher-developed interview guide, also expert-validated, to explore guidance advocates' views on school programs aiding teachers. All interview recordings were reviewed to ensure accuracy and completeness of data.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure* —The researcher secured necessary permissions from institutional authorities before data collection.

Participants were oriented on the study's purpose, ethical considerations, and confidentiality, and consent was obtained. Questionnaires were personally distributed and retrieved to maintain rapport and data integrity. Pilot testing and expert validation were conducted for both the questionnaire and interview guide. Qualitative interviews were conducted in a quiet setting, recorded with permission, and follow-up questions ensured comprehensive responses

2.6. *Data Analysis* —Frequency and percentage analyses described respondents' demographics, while means measured teachers' challenges based on guidance advocates' reports. Thematic Content Analysis was applied to interview transcripts to identify key qualitative themes, providing descriptive insights into participants' experiences and perspectives.

3. Results

This section outlined the findings and discussion of the investigation. The presentation included an in-depth analysis of the demographic-based differences of guidance advocates in terms of age and educational qualification. The section eventually presented an analysis of level of challenges faced by teachers based on school guidance advocate in terms of workload challenges, instructional challenges, social status and identity challenges, and challenges in the relationship with colleagues. Furthermore, the final portion examined the insights of school guidance advocates regarding the impact of demographic differences on professional challenges in Caraga North District, Division of Davao Oriental.

3.1. *Demographic-Based Differences in Terms of Age* —Table 1 displayed the data on the demographic-based differences in terms of age among guidance advocates in Caraga North District, Division of Davao Oriental. The frequency and percentage scores for each age group were displayed in both tabular and textual representations. The results revealed that the majority of school heads were aged 41–50 years old, with 21 respondents representing 31.82 percent of the total responses. This was followed closely

by the 51–60 age group, with 20 respondents constituting 30.30 percent. The 31–40 years old group had 10 respondents or 15.15 percent, while those aged 61 and above accounted for 8 respondents or 12.12 percent. The youngest group aged 21–30 years old, had the lowest number of respondents, with 7 or 10.61 percent. These results suggest that most guidance advocates in public secondary schools in Caraga North District, Division of Davao Oriental are within the middle-aged bracket, particularly between 41 to 60 years old.

3.2. *Level of Challenges Faced by Teachers Based on School Guidance Advocates* —

Table 1. Demographic-Based Differences in Terms of Age

No.	Age	N	Frequency	Percentage
1	21–30 years old	66	7	10.61%
2	31–40 years old	10	10	15.15%
3	41–50 years old	21	21	31.82%
4	51–60 years old	20	20	30.30%
5	61 and above	8	8	12.12%
Overall		90		100%

Table 2 showed the level of challenges faced by teachers based on school guidance advocates which was measured by four indicators namely: workload challenges, instructional challenges, social status and identity challenges, and challenges in the relationship with colleagues. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: Workload Challenges (3.63), which was described as high. Instructional Challenges (3.48) was equivalent to high, while Social Status and Identity Challenges (3.43) was described as

high. Challenges in the Relationship with Colleagues (3.50) was also described as high. The four indicators/domains on the level of challenges faced by teachers generate an overall mean rating of (3.51), described as high. This means that the challenges faced by teachers in terms of challenges, instructional challenges, social status and identity challenges, and challenges in the relationship with colleagues were oftentimes evident.

Table 2. Level of Challenges Faced by Teachers Based on School Guidance Advocates

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Level
1	Workload Challenges	3.63	High
2	Instructional Challenges	3.48	High
3	Social Status and Identity Challenges	3.43	High
4	Challenges in the Relationship with Colleagues	3.50	High
Overall Mean		3.51	High

3.3. *Insights School Guidance Advocates Provide Regarding the Impact of Demographic Differences on Their Professional Challenges*

3.3.1. *Developing Healthy Coping Strategies*—Formulating effective coping strategies for instructors confronting obstacles entails establishing techniques to mitigate stress, emotional exhaustion, and occupational pressures. Educators frequently encounter burnout as a result of substantial workloads, student con-

duct challenges, and insufficient support; thus, coping mechanisms are essential for preserving mental and emotional health.

3.3.2. *Encouraging Collaboration*—Promoting collaboration among instructors in the face of challenges entails cultivating a climate conducive to collective problem-solving of shared difficulties. This include the dissemination of best practices, tools, and solutions to address challenges in classroom administration, the creation of curriculum, and student involve-

Fig. 2. Insights School Guidance Advocates Provide Regarding the Impact of Demographic Differences on Their Professional Challenges

ment. Collaborative endeavors allow educators to devise solutions for both personal and communal difficulties, so enhancing their efficacy.

3.3.3. *Seeking Help and Support* —Requesting aid and support on the difficulties encountered by educators entails acknowledging

the necessity for help and contacting suitable resources for direction. This may entail seeking counsel from colleagues, educational leaders, or external experts to address stress, workload, or challenging student conduct.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to determine the demographic-based differences of guidance advocates in terms of age and educational qualification. Moreover, to determine the level of challenges faced by teachers based on school guidance advocate in terms of workload challenges, instructional challenges, social status and identity challenges, and challenges in the relationship with colleagues. Furthermore, the final portion examined the insights of school guidance advocates regarding the impact of demographic differences on professional challenges in Caraga North District, Division of Davao Oriental. The following are the significant findings:

On demographic-based differences of guidance advocates in terms of age results revealed that the majority of school heads were aged 41–50 years old. This was followed closely by the 51–60 age group. Then, the 31–40 years old group while those aged 61. The youngest

group aged 21–30 years old, had the lowest number of respondents. Moreover, in terms of educational qualification results revealed that the majority of guidance advocates were MA graduates. This was followed by those with MA units. Then, the Bachelor graduates and those PhD units, the lowest number of respondents was PhD graduates.

On the level of challenges faced by teachers based on the school guidance advocates in terms of workload challenges, instructional challenges, social status and identity challenges, and challenges in the relationship with colleagues were all high. These also means that the level of the challenges faced by teachers based on the school guidance advocates were oftentimes evident.

On the qualitative data, three themes emerged after the thematic content analysis. On the insights of school guidance advocates regarding the impact of demographic differences

on their professional challenges are: (1) developing healthy coping strategies, (2) encouraging collaboration, and (3) seeking help and support.

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that schools strengthen support systems for teachers through the active involvement of guidance advocates, as well-supported teachers are better equipped to manage challenges and deliver quality instruction. Teachers should seek help when needed, engage in professional de-

velopment, and build peer networks to improve their well-being. School heads are urged to implement structured support and wellness programs, while guidance advocates should focus on resilience-building and personalized support. Additionally, future research should further explore the link between teacher demographics and challenges, including long-term impacts of guidance interventions.

5. References

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